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OPPORTUNITIES OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

The opportunities today for the HE in India are:

1. Participate in high-level masters/doctoral courses.
2. Receive double/multiple/joint degree from consortium of excellent universities.
3. Improve linguistic skills, intercultural experience.
4. Improve employability of students through recognition of qualifications and study periods abroad.
5. Development of humanistic resources for the realization of social, economic, cultural consequences of universities internationalization.
6. Acquaint students with abilities and skills in the international arena.
7. The cause the effective and more international scientific and cultural cooperation among the universities and students unions.
8. Enrichment of university environments for educational and research activities according to the global standards.
9. The effective cooperation in planning, executing, accessing of the international research projects among the university.
10. Preparation of facilities for scientific boards to use new technologies.

SWOT ANALYSIS INDIAN HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR

Despite the huge potential in the higher education sector, not everyone has been able to achieve success. The challenges/threats, which the private sector players face in India, are significant and therefore, approaching the market with a well thought-out strategy is advisable.

Strengths

- Few globally renowned educational institutions
- Huge demand – estimated 150 mn population in 18-23 age group
- Growing middle class with increasing incomes
- Growing economy with numerous employment opportunities
- Huge demand for Indian students in overseas markets

Weaknesses

- Lack of infrastructure
- Shortage of trained faculty to meet the increased demand
- Highly complex and unclear regulatory framework at Central & State level.

- Regional imbalances
- “Not for profit” tag in formal education.

Opportunities

- Unsaturated demand for quality global education.
- Low GER of 15% in Higher education as compared to 84% in USA.
- Sharp decline in dependency ratio predicted in the next 30 years.
- India is expected to emerge as a Global hub in education in Asia Pacific region.
- Low focus on R&D.

Threats

- High time lag in introduction of reforms due to various reasons.
- Deterioration in quality of education specially in private sector due to lack of availability of trained faculty.
- Over regulation – control over course curriculum, entrance tests, fees, etc

CONCLUSION

The Higher Education system is witnessing significant transformations and reforms. The globalization of economic activities and development in science and technology accelerate the growth of new types of higher education institutions. In such an economic view, there is a demand for training and expertise, and universities and other higher education institutions are suppliers in the market in which this demand is voiced. They found themselves by asking a price for the commodity they offer, and they cater to those who cherish the commodity and are able to pay the price. There is a pressure on higher education institutions to gain at least some of their earnings through selling their product. The relation of such trends to globalizations is clear: this is a case of economic globalization driven by market imperatives. The prevailing system of higher education in India is not capable of starting a new era and is not competitive at the international level with the exception of few institutes. This system needs a major renovation to stand competitively in this era of globalization. In order to effectively plan for reforms and improvement, it is necessary to have in realistic perceptions what is possible and what is not.

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